

A New FPGA-based Architecture of Task Scheduler with Support of Periodic Real-Time Tasks

Lukáš Kohútka, Viera Stopjaková
Institute of Electronics and Photonics
Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava
Bratislava, Slovakia
lukas.kohutka@stuba.sk

Abstract—This paper presents a new FPGA design of a task scheduler that supports not only aperiodic hard real-time tasks but periodic tasks too. Whenever a period of a periodic task is elapsed, the task is automatically restarted with no need of software intervention. The proposed scheduler is using Earliest Deadline First (EDF) algorithm. For inter-task synchronisation, the scheduler also supports temporary suspension of tasks with automatic resumption of tasks after the specified time elapsed. The proposed architecture is based on priority queues used for time management and decision-making processes. Thanks to FPGA implementation of the scheduler and its priority queues, the scheduler operations are always performed in two clock cycles regardless of the current number of tasks and regardless of the maximum possible number of tasks in the system. The paper contains results obtained by FPGA synthesis done for various parameters using Intel FPGA Cyclone V device. The proposed solution was verified using simplified version of Universal Verification Methodology (UVM) and applying millions of test instructions with randomly generated deadline and period values.

Keywords—task scheduling, real-time, EDF, FPGA, periodic tasks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Real-time systems are embedded systems that contain real-time tasks. The execution of real-time tasks can be successful only these tasks are completed before the task deadline is met. In other words, the success of real-time tasks depends on timing of these tasks too. Even if real-time tasks are running on the most powerful processor with the highest possible performance, we have no guarantee that all real-time tasks will be completed on time. For this reason, real-time systems need to use a task scheduler that is scheduling real-time tasks. Real-time task scheduling is supposed to guarantee that all real-time tasks always meet their deadlines [1].

Real-time task schedulers are usually implemented in software, but these software-based solutions are facing several issues. An ideal real-time task scheduler is supposed to always create the best possible schedule that represents optimum order of tasks. In addition to this, an ideal task scheduler requires zero processor time for performing the scheduling itself. Ideally, we want to use all the CPU time for execution of the scheduled task and not for the scheduling. Of course, this is rather idealistic view, and the real schedulers will always consume at least some of the CPU time. Therefore, a

more realistic requirement would be that the CPU time spent for task scheduling is minimum possible and constant too. The constant time of task scheduling improves the predictability and determinism of the whole real-time system significantly. The software-implemented task schedulers are very limited in task scheduling algorithms that are being used because of the requirement for constant and low amount of CPU time spent for task scheduling. As a result, these software-implemented schedulers are mostly based on priorities, not the actual deadlines of real-time tasks. This leads to lack of robustness and efficiency in scheduling itself. A possible solution to these problems is hardware acceleration. Real-time task schedulers can be implemented in hardware, which allows to use deadline-based scheduling algorithms, to minimize the time spent for scheduling and make it constant too [1-3].

The existing task schedulers that are implemented in hardware are mostly applicable for very simple systems that consist of aperiodic hard real-time tasks only. These solutions are not suitable for more complex, robust real-time systems with higher number of tasks and bigger variability of task types. Therefore, a more robust and complex task scheduler with a support of various types of tasks is required [1-12].

Real-time systems often contain periodic tasks in addition to aperiodic tasks too. Even though periodic tasks can be handled by task schedulers the same way as aperiodic tasks, adding a dedicated support of periodic tasks directly inside the HW-based scheduler improves the overall system performance because no further software extension for periodic tasks management would be needed [13, 14].

II. RELATED WORK

One of the most popular task scheduling algorithms for real-time systems is Earliest Deadline First (EDF), which is proven to always generate an optimum schedule for aperiodic hard real-time tasks [1, 2]. This algorithm keeps sorting all tasks according to their deadlines so that the task with the earliest deadline (i.e. the lowest deadline value) is selected for execution. All tasks that are ready for execution but not actually running, are stored in a structure called “ready queue”, which is priority queue. Such priority queues can be implemented by various sorting architectures, such as shift registers architecture [15] or systolic array architecture [16].

In our previous work published in [17-20], we already presented various task schedulers implemented as coprocessor

units. A slightly modified version of EDF algorithm was implemented to also support killing/removing tasks according to task ID, which is a standard feature needed in modern operating systems. The ability of killing any task according to its ID is providing more flexibility and better extensibility of the proposed HW solution with additional features that can be implemented in software, such as inter-task communication and task synchronization, as well as support of non-RT tasks.

Apart from our research, there are also many other existing solutions available. Some solutions are using EDF algorithm [11, 12, 15]. Other solutions are based on priorities and/or static scheduling instead of deadlines, which represents less efficient scheduling for RT systems in general [8-10, 22-25]. These solutions are suitable for less complex systems consisting of simple aperiodic real-time tasks only.

Some solutions are also using a method for monitoring of remaining execution time of real-time tasks and prediction of possible deadline misses too [26-28].

III. PROPOSED SCHEDULER

A. Top-level module

The proposed scheduler is designed in a form of a coprocessor unit that is getting instructions from CPU and providing instruction results back to the CPU. This means that the scheduler is expected to be wrapped by / integrated into an existing CPU, similarly as arithmetic coprocessors or any other coprocessor units. Figure 1 shows a top module of the proposed scheduler that consists of 7 components: Semaphore, Control Unit, Running Tasks, Tasks Memory, Idle Queue, Waiting Queue and Ready Queue.

The top module has two inputs only (called *instr_0* and *instr_1*) – the instructions provided by a CPU that can execute two instructions in parallel (e.g. dual-core CPUs). The *output* of the top module is used to provide, useful information back to CPU. In this way, CPU knows which two tasks are selected for execution/running at the moment and CPU can read *memory_output* from Tasks Memory too.

Fig. 1. Top-level module of proposed scheduler

The following coprocessor instructions are supported by the proposed task scheduler:

- **WR_TASK_MEMORY** – inserts a new task into Tasks Memory of task scheduler or modifies an existing task. This instruction performs standard write operation into the memory.
- **RD_TASK_MEMORY** – reads an existing task from Tasks Memory of task scheduler. This instruction performs standard read operation from the memory.
- **TASK_SCHEDULE** – schedules an instance of a created task for task execution, which will cause that the task is moved into Ready Queue or Running Tasks depending on scheduling decision (deadlines), and the state of the task in Tasks Memory will be updated too.
- **TASK_KILL** – de-schedules (i.e. kills) a scheduled instance of a task, which removes the task from the scheduler queues including Running Tasks module and sets the state of the task in Tasks Memory to **IDLE_TASK**.

- **TASK_BLOCK** – sets a state of an existing task to **WAITING_TASK** and moves the task to Waiting Queue. A specific time (called waiting time) is also provided to determine how long the task shall wait before it is automatically unblocked.
- **TASK_UNBLOCK** – releases (unblocks) an existing waiting task from **WAITING_TASK** state and removes the task from Waiting Queue, returning the task back to Ready Queue or Running Tasks. This instruction is used to unblock the task sooner than the waiting time elapses.
- **GET_RUNNING_TASK** – provides the currently running task for the given CPU core via task scheduler output, which is obtained from Running Tasks module.

B. Ready Queue

Ready Queue is a component that contains all tasks that are ready for execution but not selected for execution at the moment because there are other tasks with earlier deadlines. The Ready Queue component is implemented as priority queue, which means that all ready tasks are being sorted so that this component is prepared to provide the next task for execution whenever it is needed. Tasks are sorted according to task deadlines. This component is based on existing sorting architecture called Shift Registers, which consists of task cells. Each task cell contains one task comparator, control logic and a register to store one task ID with task deadline. The task cells can exchange tasks with adjacent task cells. Each task cell receives the same instruction in parallel using shared bus. An example of the Shift Registers architecture with four cells is given in Figure 2 [21].

Fig. 2. Shift Registers architecture

C. Waiting Queue

Waiting Queue is a component that contains all tasks that were temporarily suspended/blocked using **TASK_BLOCK** instruction. The Waiting Queue component is implemented as priority queue, the same way as Ready Queue. The suspended/blocked tasks are also called waiting tasks as they are waiting for unblocking by one of two reasons: either instruction **TASK_UNBLOCK** is called or the waiting time of the given task elapses. The unblocking of waiting task causes that the waiting task is removed from the Waiting Queue. Tasks are sorted according to remaining waiting times of the tasks.

D. Idle Queue

Idle Queue is a component that contains all periodic tasks that are in idle state at the moment, i.e. these tasks were either naturally completed or killed using instruction **TASK_KILL**. The Idle Queue is relevant for periodic tasks only. If the task is not periodic, then it is not stored into Idle Queue at all. The Idle Queue component is implemented as priority queue, the same way as Ready Queue or Waiting Queue. Tasks are sorted according to remaining period times of the tasks. The output of the Idle Queue is the idle periodic task that will complete its period as the next one. When the period is met (i.e. when current time is equal to the period time of the task) then the output task of the Idle Queue should be removed from the Idle Queue and scheduled again. In this way, any number of periodic tasks can be handled efficiently. If multiple tasks are supposed to be rescheduled at the simultaneously, then these tasks can be handled in any order and the later rescheduled tasks need to adjust the remaining deadline by this delay.

E. Semaphore

The component called Semaphore is responsible for resolving conflicts whenever multiple CPU cores want to use the scheduler coprocessor at the same clock cycle. This module arbitrates the instructions and selects one of them that is passed to Control Unit. The other instruction is stalled for the time being. The Semaphore component is using Round-Robin algorithm to ensure load-balancing and fairness of the arbitration. Figure 3 shows the logic circuit that implements Semaphore component.

Fig. 3. Semaphore component

F. Running Tasks

The Running Tasks component contains the currently running tasks, i.e. tasks that are selected for execution at the moment. The capacity of this component is 2 tasks, meaning that there are up to two tasks being executed at a time. This component is also responsible for avoiding unnecessary task/context switches by moving the already running task from one CPU core to another one. Thanks to this, the amount of task/context switches is minimized resulting in minimum

overhead of the scheduling, depending only on the scheduling itself.

Figure 4 depicts the logic circuit that represents the Running Tasks module. The circuit contains four sets of registers (task ID of CPU core 1, task deadline of CPU core 1, task ID of CPU core 2, and task deadline of CPU core 2) and

one 1-bit register (in the upper-right corner of the circuit) that remembers which of these two tasks has later deadline. For this comparison, one comparator is needed only. The second comparator is used for comparison of the task with the higher deadline value with deadline of the new, incoming task. The NAND and AND logic gates are used only for enabling of the registers that contain the running tasks.

Fig. 4. Running Tasks component

G. Control Unit

This component is responsible for controlling all task queues (Running Tasks, Ready Queue, Waiting Queue and Idle Queue) and for writing to and reading from the Tasks Memory. Whenever a new valid instruction is provided from Semaphore component, Control Unit decodes and executes this instruction by sending the control and data bits to other components. Basically, all task queue components are controlled by Control Unit directly, except for Ready Queue, which is accessed indirectly only, through the Running Tasks component. Even if no instruction is provided from CPU/Semaphore, the Control Unit can still automatically move tasks between the Idle Queue and Running Tasks, and between the Waiting Queue and Running Tasks. In this way,

the handling of blocked/waiting tasks as well as idle periodic tasks is fully autonomous, which leads to minimum usage of processor time for task management in general, which is especially important for real-time tasks.

H. Tasks Memory

This component is a standard memory with multiple ports that are needed for multiple features implemented in other components. Because of the several ports needed for reading and writing to the memory, this memory is implemented with registers, otherwise it could be theoretically implemented using SRAM too. The register-based implementation is less area-efficient, but the extra ports are needed for multiple features explained in other components.

This memory contains all tasks, which are represented by task type, current state of the task, parent ID of the task, and several various timing characteristics of the task, such as deadline, period and execution time of the task. The memory map of Tasks Memory component is displayed in Table I. The lowest 3 bits of the address are used to select a particular part of data for the same task. The remaining upper bits of address are used for task selection.

TABLE I. MEMORY MAP OF TASKS MEMORY

Address [2:0]	Item	Bits
0	parent ID	8
1	task type & task state	5 + 4
2	remaining deadline	20
3	remaining period	20
4	remaining execution time	20
5	starting deadline	20
6	starting period	20
7	starting execution time	20

IV. VERIFICATION

The proposed coprocessor was described and verified using SystemVerilog language. The verification consists of simulations that are based on simplified version of Universal Verification Methodology (UVM), which means that only SystemVerilog language was used with no UVM libraries. We created one test procedure that can randomly generate millions of instructions for Design Under Test (DUT) inputs and a predictor that serves as a reference model and is predicting expected outputs of the DUT. The expected outputs provided by predictor are being compared to the actual output of the DUT. Our test procedure generates millions of instructions consisting of various fixed instruction opcodes and task IDs and randomized timing values, such as deadlines, execution times and period times.

V. SYNTHESIS RESULTS

The proposed task scheduler was synthesized into Intel FPGA Cyclone V, device 5CSEBA6U23I7. For the synthesis, we used tool Intel Quartus Prime 16.1 (Lite Edition). We also performed static timing analysis to report maximum clock frequency that is possible for each version of the design.

The resource costs as well as the maximum clock frequency depend on the maximum number of tasks the scheduler can contain, also known as Tasks Capacity. The higher the Tasks Capacity parameter is, the more logic and worse timing is achieved. Table II is showing the synthesis results. For the given FPGA family, the logic utilization is

defined by Adaptive Logic Modules (ALM) consumption. We used 20 bits for implementation of each timing variable (deadline, waiting time, execution time). The task ID consists of 8 bits.

TABLE II. FPGA SYNTHESIS RESULTS

Tasks Capacity	Adaptive Logic Modules (ALM)	Registers	Maximum Clock Frequency (MHz)
8	309	305	178,99
16	566	521	157,68
24	807	736	138,45
32	1042	956	128,27
40	1299	1161	122,25
48	1551	1383	118,20
56	1792	1604	107,54
64	2019	1813	105,57

The synthesis results are showing that all versions of the proposed scheduler are working with a clock that is set to 105 MHz or more. The resource costs are relatively small too, since the FPGA devices have nowadays hundreds of thousands or even millions of Adaptive Logic Modules.

VI. FUTURE IMPROVEMENTS

The proposed scheduler was optimized for RT systems that are using dual-core CPUs only. However, the scheduler can be improved by extending the support of two CPU cores to four CPU cores simultaneously by applying the same approaches that were already used for two cores.

Another improvement can be achieved by implementing support of soft real-time tasks in addition to the existing support of hard real-time tasks and non-real-time tasks.

Additionally, an optimization of the three priority queues (Ready Queue, Idle Queue and Waiting Queue) used inside the scheduler can lead to significant optimization of the whole scheduler because these priority queues have the highest impact on synthesis results of the scheduler. This would allow scaling the design for higher Tasks Capacity.

VII. CONCLUSION

We proposed a new task scheduler that performs EDF scheduling algorithm and is implemented on FPGA. The proposed scheduler is suitable for robust real-time systems that can contain aperiodic hard real-time tasks, periodic hard real-time tasks and best-effort (non-real-time) tasks. The proposed solution uses an approach that is based on the priority queues. The priority queue structure is used not only for sorting of ready tasks but for periodic idle tasks and blocked/waiting tasks too. Thanks to the priority queues, handling of periodic idle tasks and blocked/waiting tasks is

efficient and simple. The handling of periodic tasks and waiting tasks is fully autonomous, requiring no software intervention apart from the initial configuration of Tasks Memory. Thanks to that, the proposed scheduler is very efficient in managing periodic tasks and is very suitable for further software extension containing task synchronization and inter-task communication.

The proposed scheduler can be used for dual-core CPUs, i.e. CPUs that are executing two tasks in parallel. All instructions that are supported by the proposed scheduler require only 2 clock cycles to perform, regardless of system configuration and actual or maximum number of tasks in the system, assuming no conflicts between the two CPU cores. If both CPU cores are trying to use the scheduler at the same time, then this conflict can cause a delay of 2 clock cycles, resulting in 4 cycle latency per instruction in total.

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REFERENCES

- [1] G. Buttazzo, "Hard Real-Time Computing Systems: Predictable Scheduling Algorithms and Applications," 2011.
- [2] G. Buttazzo, J. Stankovic, "Adding robustness in dynamic preemptive scheduling," In D. S. Fussell and M. Malek (eds.), *Responsive Computer Systems: Steps Toward Fault-Tolerant Real-Time Systems*. Boston: Kluwer Academic Publishers, 1995.
- [3] M. Caccamo and G. Buttazzo, "Optimal scheduling for fault-tolerant and firm real-time systems," *Proceedings Fifth International Conference on Real-Time Computing Systems and Applications (Cat. No.98EX236)*, Hiroshima, Japan, 1998, pp. 223-231.
- [4] G. C. Buttazzo and F. Sensini, "Optimal deadline assignment for scheduling soft aperiodic tasks in hard real-time environments," in *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, vol. 48, no. 10, pp. 1035-1052, Oct. 1999.
- [5] G. Buttazzo, F. Conticelli, G. Lamastra and G. Lipari, "Robot control in hard real-time environment," *Proceedings Fourth International Workshop on Real-Time Computing Systems and Applications*, Taipei, Taiwan, 1997, pp. 152-159.
- [6] M. Spuri, G. Buttazzo, F. Sensini, "Robust aperiodic scheduling under dynamic priority systems," *Proceedings 16th IEEE Real-Time Systems Symposium*, Pisa, 1995, pp. 210-219.
- [7] M. Gergeleit, L. B. Becker, E. Nett, "Robust scheduling in team-robotics," *Proceedings International Parallel and Distributed Processing Symposium*, Nice, France, 2003, pp. 8.
- [8] A. Norollah, D. Derafshi, H. Beitollahi and M. Fazeli, "RTHS: A Low-Cost High-Performance Real-Time Hardware Sorter, Using a Multidimensional Sorting Algorithm," in *IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems*, vol. 27, no. 7, pp. 1601-1613, July 2019.
- [9] D. Derafshi, A. Norollah, M. Khosroanjani and H. Beitollahi, "HRHS: A High-Performance Real-Time Hardware Scheduler" in *IEEE Transactions on Parallel & Distributed Systems*, vol. 31, no. 04, pp. 897-908, 2020. doi: 10.1109/TPDS.2019.2952136.
- [10] C. Suman and G. Kumar, "Performance Enhancement of Real Time System using Dynamic Scheduling Algorithms," 2019 IEEE 5th International Conference for Convergence in Technology (I2CT), Bombay, India, 2019, pp. 1-6.
- [11] Teraiya, J., Shah, A. Optimized scheduling algorithm for soft Real-Time System using particle swarm optimization technique. *Evol. Intel.* (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12065-021-00599-6>.
- [12] A. Norollah, Z. Kazemi, N. Sayadi, H. Beitollahi, M. Fazeli and D. Hely, "Efficient Scheduling of Dependent Tasks in Many-Core Real-Time System Using a Hardware Scheduler," 2021 IEEE High Performance Extreme Computing Conference (HPEC), 2021, pp. 1-7, doi: 10.1109/HPEC49654.2021.9622857.
- [13] O. Kotaba, J. Nowotsch, M. Paulitsch, S. M. Petters, H. Theiling, "Multicore in Real-Time Systems - Temporal Isolation Challenges due to Shared Resources", CISTER technical report, 2014.
- [14] E. Wandeler, A. Maxiaguine, L. Thiele, "Quantitative Characterization of Event Streams in Analysis of Hard Real-Time Applications", in *Real-Time Systems*, vol. 29, pp. 205-225, 2005 Springer. doi: 10.1007/s11241-005-6885-x.
- [15] G. Bloom, G. Parmer, B. Narahari, and R. Simha, "Shared Hardware Data Structures for Hard Real-Time Systems," *Proceedings of the tenth ACM international conference on Embedded software*, 2012.
- [16] S.W. Moon, "Scalable Hardware Priority Queue Architectures for High-Speed Packet Switches," *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, 2000.
- [17] L. Kohutka, M. Vojtko, and T. Krajcovic, "Hardware Accelerated Scheduling in Real-Time Systems," *Engineering of Computer Based Systems Eastern European Regional Conference*, 2015.
- [18] L. Kohutka, V. Stopjakova, "Hardware-Accelerated Task Scheduling in Real-Time Systems: Deadline Based Coprocessor for Dual-Core CPUs," *International Symposium on Design and Diagnostics of Electronic Circuits and Systems*, 2016.
- [19] L. Kohutka, V. Stopjakova, "Task Scheduler for Dual-Core Real-Time Systems," *International Conference on Mixed Design of Integrated Circuits and Systems*, 2016.
- [20] L. Kohutka, V. Stopjakova, "Improved Task Scheduler for Dual-Core Real-Time Systems," *Euromicro Conference on Digital System Design*, 2016.
- [21] Y. Tang, and N.W. Bergmann, "A Hardware Scheduler Based on Task Queues for FPGA-Based Embedded Real-Time Systems," *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, 2015.
- [22] J. Stamer, J. Adomat, J. Furunas, and L. Lindh, "Real-Time Scheduling Co-Processor in Hardware for Single and Multiprocessor Systems," *Proceedings of the EUROMICRO Conference*, 1996.
- [23] C. Ferreira, and A.S.R. Oliveira, "Hardware Co-Processor for the OReK Real-Time Executive," 2010.
- [24] S.E. Ong, and S.C. Lee, "SEOS: Hardware Implementation of Real-Time Operating System for Adaptability," *Computing and Networking (CANDAR)*, 2013 First International Symposium, 2013.
- [25] K. Kim, D. Kim, and Ch. Park, "Real-Time Scheduling in Heterogeneous Dual-core Architectures," *Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Parallel and Distributed Systems*, 2006.
- [26] A. Kritikakou, C. Pagetti, O. Baldellon, M. Roy, C. Rochange, "Run-time Control to Increase Task Parallelism in Mixed-Critical Systems," in 26th Euromicro Conf. on Real-Time Systems, 2014 IEEE. doi: 10.1109/ECRTS.2014.14.
- [27] A. Kritikakou C. Pagetti, C. Rochange, M. Faugere, S. Girbal, D. Gracia Perez, "Distributed Run-time WCET Controller for concurrent critical tasks in Mixed-Critical Systems" in Proc. of the 22nd Int. Conf. on Real-Time Networks and Systems, 2014 ACM. doi: 10.1145/2659787.2659799.
- [28] Angeliki Kritikakou, Thibaut Marty, and Matthieu Roy. 2017. DYNASCORE: DYNAMIC Software CONTROLLER to Increase RESOURCE Utilization in Mixed-Critical Systems. *ACM Trans. Des. Autom. Electron. Syst.* 23, 2, Article 13 (October 2017), 26 pages. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3110222>